

Original Paper

Experiment on Inverted Fractal Corresponds with Cosmological Observations and Conjectures

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Abstract: In a recent paper—The Fractal Corresponds to Light and Quantum Foundation Problems—the author described the forward-looking progressive perspective of a fractal. In this paper, the author modelled the complementary and dual perspectives of the same fractal, specifically its retrospective perspective in cosmology. Recent discussions as to whether the universe is fractal concluded with the 2012 WiggleZ Dark Energy Survey findings in (part) agreement with fractal-cosmology proponents that the small-scale observable universe is fractal; however, beyond this, the smooth large-scale—and thus the universe—is not fractal. Is this smoothness and other Λ CDM properties what one would expect to observe (within) if the universe is a fractal? Current fractal-cosmology models seek repeating patterns at larger scales farther out. Although these structures have since been found in the smooth, in this paper, growth from the perspective of a growing fractal was modelled. An experiment was conducted on a ‘simple’ (Koch snowflake) fractal. New triangle sizes of arbitrary size were held constant, and earlier triangles were allowed to expand as the fractal set iterated (grew). Classical kinematic equations—velocity and acceleration—were calculated for the total area and the distance between arbitrary points. Hubble-Lemaître's Law, accelerated expansion, a changing acceleration rate—decreasing with time—and a changing size distribution, all consistent with cosmological observations and conjectures, were tested. Results showed: the area expanded exponentially from an arbitrary starting size; and as a consequence, the distances between measured points—from any location within the set—receded away from the ‘observer’ at increasing velocities and accelerations. It was concluded that the universe is not only fractal, but also is a fractal. At the expense of the cosmological principle, the fractal is a geometric match to cosmological observations and conjectures, capable of demonstrating the inflationary epoch, the Hubble-Lemaître expansion, accelerated expansion, and a changing rate of

expansion. Large-scale smoothness is a property of growing fractals and is expected. From this model—from planet Earth—we are observing within ‘the branches’, looking out and back in time to ‘the boughs’ (the large quasar structures) and ‘the trunk’ (the CMB, which was once seedling-sized, Planck-area-sized) of a fractal-shaped universe. Other problems—including the horizon problem and the vacuum catastrophe—were addressed. Based on previous work on quantum fractals, the fractal may offer a direct mechanism to unify quantum and cosmological problems—unifying the two realities as two aspects of the same modern geometry.

Keywords: Cosmological Principle, Dark Energy, Inflation, Hubble-Lemaitre’s Law, Quantum Gravity, Quantum Cosmology

1 Introduction

This paper should be read in conjunction with the author’s companion paper: The Fractal Corresponds to Light and Quantum Foundation Problems [1].

Based on observations, the universe is not only expanding from a conjectured ‘big bang’ singularity, but this expansion is accelerating. These claims are derived, respectively, from the late 1920s Hubble galaxy observations[2] (Figure 1a) and Lemaitre[3] mathematics; the 1964 Penzias and Wilson discovery of the cosmic microwave background (CMB) [4] (Figure 1c), and the 1998 supernova observations of accelerated expansion by Riess et al. [5] and Perlmutter et al.[6]. These discoveries, along with the so-called ‘dark matter’—that is pulling and holding the universe together—form the Standard ‘Lambda Cold Dark Matter’ (Λ CDM) Model of Cosmology. As successful and outstanding a human achievement as this model is, it is, however, by all accounts, in a self-titled crisis. Nobody—it is claimed by many—has any idea how to ‘make sense of it’, let alone be able to marry it in any ‘simple’ way with its equal enigma, our quantum reality.

Notwithstanding these problems, the standard model is also based on Albert Einstein’s 1915 General Relativity, which in turn—fundamentally—assumes that the cosmological principle holds on all cosmological scales. The cosmological principle assumes that no matter one’s observation position in the universe—be it, for instance, at the outer edge of the observable universe—one should observe similar ‘smooth and uniform’ (homogenous) distribution patterns throughout and in all (isotropic) directions. The universe should be homogenous and isotropic on all cosmic scales; however, by observations (Figure 2), it appears not to be the case, and this is problematic.

The first large-scale astronomical surveys of galaxies, beginning in the 1980s, quickly revealed this counter of the cosmological principle. They found (Figure 1 b, and also surveys included in Figure 1 c) as we look further out, galaxies are distributed in ‘clusters’ followed by ‘super-clusters’—at least on ‘small cosmic scales’

a

b

(a) The original Hubble Diagram showing the relationship between the recession velocity of galaxies by their distance[2];

(b) 2003 2df Redshift Survey among the first surveys to show small-scale 'fractal' clustering[7];

(c) The Log. mass-density curve of the universe by measurement method showing rough and dense galaxy distribution near Earth out to the smooth CMB 'edge';

(d) The WiggleZ Dark Energy Survey figure 13, page 16 of the Wigglez survey, corresponding to 'a' and revealing changing galaxy distributions from small-scale to large-scale [8].

Figure 1. Redshift Survey Evolution.

1.1 Fractal-Cosmology

One geometric candidate to explain this 'small-scale galactic structure anomaly'—posited soon after its conception and long after Einstein's work—was the fractal [9]. Fractals are known as the geometry of chaos[10] and are defined by the 'epic' Mandelbrot Set—named after the discoverer and fractal name-giver, Benoit Mandelbrot[11]. They are a scale-free mathematical object that is based on the recursion or iteration of a 'simple' pattern (for the Mandelbrot set, $z_{n+1} = z_n^2 + c$ [9]) and are a well-accepted mathematical description of our reality, with examples including trees, clouds, and market prices. From fractals, a new field of cosmology—fractal-cosmology—was formed [12]. Fractals do not appear homogeneous or isotropic and thus would challenge the standard model. In the late 1990s, a debate ensued over whether the observed clustering and super-clustering galaxy distribution is fractal [12]. Proponents—the fractal cosmologists—argued that, with better

technology, even larger galactic structures would be discovered beyond those then observed [13],[14],[15],[16],[17]. The opponents, Hogg and others, argued: yes, the universe appears rough and fractal at small scales, but at large scales it is smooth; therefore, the cosmological principle holds [18].

The debate came to a head with the findings of the 2012 WiggleZ Dark Energy Survey[8] (Figure 1d), and others [19]. It was concluded—but granted—that the universe does indeed show direct evidence of small-scale fractal galaxy distribution for distances less than 70 to 100 megaparsecs away (3 billion light-years); however, the universe is assumed overall ‘smooth’, homogenous and isotropic, beyond this on large scales. As it stands today—for cosmology—‘fractals are out’[20]. Meanwhile, not long after the WiggleZ survey paper was released, improved large-scale surveys were revealing ‘very large’, ‘thin’, and ‘old’ galactic structures in the assumed ‘smooth universe’. They are the 4 billion light-years-sized ‘Large Quasar Group’[21], and the 10 billion light-years-sized Hercules Corona Borealis Great Wall [22]). These structures are beyond the small—granted fractal—scale and contradict all of the above fractal rebuttals. Today, at the time of writing, it appears that the debate over a fractal universe has passed, and nothing has been made of the predicted and expected (by the proponents) observed LQGs.

Figure 2 is ‘The map of the observable Universe’ [23]; the latest from the 2020 DESI survey. The DESI survey is an exquisite visualisation of the observable universe, showing the evolution and distribution of galaxies and the absolute differences between small-scale and large-scale structure. This map is arguably not in accord with the cosmological principle. Viewing from the outreaches is not the same as viewing from planet Earth. To the left, from Earth, we see the clustering and superclusters observed in early surveys. This is followed by (firstly) the red and the blue ‘old’ (LQG—quasar) smoothing out to the ‘origins’ CMB limit.

Showing the changing distribution and demographics of galaxy structure observed from Earth (left) out to the cosmic microwave background (right).

Figure 2. The DESI Map of the Observable Universe[23].

Can a different perspective or model of the fractal, that assumes general relativity as a given, help explain all of the cosmic observations and conjectures? Is the ‘rough’ to ‘smooth’ pattern—as shown in Figure 2—expanding from a point beginning exactly what one would expect to observe if observing within a fractal? Is it that the universe—as the fractal cosmologists currently claim—is not only fractal

but that it is a fractal in its totality? Do we have the fractal model wrong? To test these questions, we need to study the growth of a fractal from the perspective of a fractal.

1.2 The Inverted Fractal Model

Current fractal cosmology studies assume a traditional, or classical, perspective on fractal growth, popularised by the example of Romanesco broccoli. This is a ‘forward-looking’ *progressive* perspective on the fractal set, best exemplified by the Koch snowflake. From this perspective, ‘fractal-cosmologists’ seek repeated larger-scale patterns or structures further out and do not think of the growth of the fractal.

Figure 3a shows the growth of the convergent ‘snowflake’ fractal structure that emerges to a limit size at around 7 番 2 iterations by the addition of new but diminishing-sized bits (blue 1 and green 2) to the initial constant-sized (thatched red ‘0’) triangle bit. This progressive perspective of the fractal is explained and analysed by the author in the paper ‘The Fractal Corresponds to Light and Quantum Foundation Problems’[1].

However, the fractal can—simultaneously—be modelled from an alternative *retrospective* or -looking behind perspective (Figure 3b) that better focuses on the actual growth behaviour of the fractal.

The schematics above demonstrate fractal development by (a) the (classical) forward or evolving Snowflake perspective, where the standard-sized thatched (iteration ‘0’) is the focus, and the following triangles diminish in size from colour red iteration 0 to colour green iteration 2. (b) The inverted retrospective perspective assumes a fixed location within the fractal. The new (thatched) triangle is the

focus and held at standard size, while the original red iteration 0 triangle expands in area, as the fractal iterates.

Figure 3. Dual Perspectives of (Koch Snowflake) Fractal Growth.

To model this retrospective perspective, the fractal was 'inverted'. Bits that were set to diminish in the classical perspective were set to grow. The new thatched bit sizes remain constant in size (the same size as the original bit size '0'), while the older generations of bit sizes increase with iteration time, as demonstrated by the colours red (the original size), blue (the 1st iteration), and green (the 2nd). With iteration time, the size of the initial red iteration-0 triangle increases relative to the size of the new blue triangle.

The closest analogy or practical example of this fractal model may be to think of the growth and structure of a tree—an example of a 'natural' fractal. This is not to say that the universe is like a tree, but rather that a tree is a fractal, and fractals come in many forms. Maybe the universe is one form. Is it that we are observing the universe as if in a tree structure, from a position of the outer branches? Surrounded by other similar-sized branches, we see, looking back and down, larger branches, then the boughs and finally the once seedling-sized twig, the trunk. All new branches, on average, start at a similar size to the seedling size and expand with time. On a mature tree, there will be many young seedling-sized branches on its outer. To complement this tree analogy, in a recent paper, it was found that all trees accelerate in size with age [24].

An empirical study was conducted on a Koch Snowflake. Distances looking back from an arbitrary observation point were measured and analysed.

Figure 4 shows the observer, represented by an eye image, at (arbitrary) iteration-time 4 (t_4) within the growing fractal. The observation point is located at an arbitrary position within the potentially infinite, scale-free, fractal set. This topic of location/'position'/measurement' is addressed in the author's complementary paper[1]. The blue lines show the displacement between the observer and the centre points of the equilibrium triangles of earlier ages (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3).

Showing the displacement between a fixed observation position (eye t_4) and retrospective points on the iterating (Koch snowflake) fractal

Figure 4. Displacement Measurements within an Iterating Fractal

In this investigation, the following questions were addressed regarding the retrospective recursive fractal from the perspective of an observer within it.

1. Does the fractal demonstrate accelerated expansion?
2. Can a Hubble-Lemaitre diagram be produced from the observing perspective of an arbitrary location within the set?
3. Does the fractal expand from a single-point Planck area to an arbitrary size of 1 in a time comparable to the conjectured inflation epoch?
4. Concerning arbitrary centre points of component fractal bits (triangles in the Koch snowflake), does the distribution of these bits change depending on the location of the observer?

It was hypothesised that current observations of the universe are all that one would expect to see if one were observing within a growing fractal that began at a single point. Specifically, the retrospective fractal will demonstrate:

1. a 'singularity' (Big Bang) like beginning; the presence, and dominance of a 'uniform' 'edge' corresponding to a Cosmic Microwave Background limit;
2. inflation epoch expansion;
3. accelerating (exponential) 'dark energy' expansion;
4. a cosmological constant;
5. a Hubble-Lemaitre Law of expansion[25],[3];
6. the retrospective fractal model will—with respect to galaxy distribution and demographics—contravene the two assumptions of the cosmological principle.

To test these questions, a model of the fractal was developed to measure changes in area and displacement with each iteration from a fixed observation point.

2 Methods

To analyse and address the said questions, a spreadsheet model—Inverted (Koch Snowflake) Fractal Model [26]—was developed to trace the area expansion of the retrospective fractal by iteration time. The classical Koch Snowflake area equations were adapted to account for this perspective. A quantitative data series was made ready for analysis. The scope of this investigation was limited to two-dimensional space for illustrative purposes; three-dimensional space or volume can be inferred from this initial assumption. Changes in the areas of triangles and distances between points in the fractal set were measured and analysed to determine whether the fractal area and distance between points expand.

2.1 Area Expansion of the Total Inverted Fractal with Iteration-time

To answer question 1, the following tables were produced. A data table was produced (Table 1) to calculate the area growth at each iteration time for a single triangle. The area (A) of a single triangle was calculated from the following equation (1) measured in standard (arbitrary) centimetres (cm)

$$A = \frac{l^2 \sqrt{3}}{4} \quad (1)$$

where l is the triangle's base length. l was set in Table 1 to 1.51967128766173 cm so that the area of the first triangle (t_0) approximated an arbitrary area of 1 cm^2 . To expand the triangle with iteration time, the base length was multiplied by a factor of 3. The iteration count was placed in a column, followed by the base length of the equilateral triangle; in the final column, the formula for calculating the triangle area was provided. Calculations were performed through the 10th iteration, and the results were plotted.

With iteration, new triangles are (in discrete quantities) introduced into the set. While the areas of new triangles remain constant, the earlier triangles expand, and by this, the total fractal set expands. To calculate the area, change of a total inverted fractal (as it iterated), the area of the single triangle (at each iteration-time) was multiplied by its corresponding quantity of triangles (at each iteration-time).

Two data tables (Tables 3 and 4 in the spreadsheet file) were developed. Table 3 was filled with the calculated triangle areas at each corresponding iteration time, from the triangle's birth through iteration 10. Table 4: triangle areas of Table 3 were multiplied by the number of triangles in the series corresponding to their iteration time. Values calculated in Tables 3 and 4 were totalled and analysed in a new table (Table 5). Analysed were: total area expansion per iteration, expansion ratio, expansion velocity, expansion acceleration, and expansion acceleration ratio. Calculations in the columns used the kinematic equations developed below.

To answer question 3, the total area expansion per iteration equation was used to calculate the time required to expand from one size to another. The time taken was calculated by setting the initial

triangle area (the Planck area) using the Planck length constant ($1.61619926 \times 10^{-35}$) and the final area was set to an arbitrary area size of 1 (cm).

2.2 Acceleration

Acceleration (a) was calculated by the following equation

$$a = \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta t} \tag{2}$$

Acceleration is measured in standard units per iteration cm^{-1t-2} and cm^{-2t-2} . Using the same methods as used to develop the Hubble diagram (as described above in 2.3) an ‘acceleration vs. distance’ diagram was created, and an expansion constant derived. Ratios of displacement expansion and acceleration were calculated by dividing the outcome of t_1 by the outcome of t_0 .

The same method of ratio calculation was used to determine the change or expansion of the area.

2.3 Distance and Displacement, Hubble-Lemaitre Diagram

To answer question 2, distances between an arbitrary observation position and points on retrospective triangle bits were measured and analysed. Calculations were performed in a second data table (Table 2) in the spreadsheet.

Measuring the blue line displacement (D) and the red line distance (d) from an observer (t_4) to the triangle centre points inside an iterating Koch Snowflake fractal. t = iteration-time.

Figure 5. Measurement of Displacement and Distance Inside a Fractal.

Triangle geometric centre points were chosen as the points of measurement, as shown in Figure 5. The blue and red lines trace the displacement (D) and distance (d), respectively, between an arbitrary observation point at t_0 and triangle centre points (t_1 , t_2 , and t_3). Calculating displacement was outside the scope of this study; distances were measured instead. Distances were measured by calculating the inscribed radius for each equilateral triangle using by equation (3) below. The total distance between points was calculated by adding the inscribed radius of the first triangle, for example, from t_0 to the inscribed radius of the next expanded triangle t_1 .

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} l \tag{3}$$

From the radius distance measurements, total distance, distance expansion ratio, velocity, acceleration, and expansion acceleration ratio for every iteration time were calculated using classical mechanics equations. Velocity (v) was calculated by the following equation

$$v = \frac{\Delta d}{\Delta t} \tag{4}$$

where distance (d). Velocity is measured in standard units per iteration cm^{-1t-1} for receding points and cm^{-2t-1} for the increasing area.

To test for Hubble's Law, a Hubble-like scatter graph titled 'The Fractal/Hubble diagram' was constructed from the results of the recession velocity and distance calculations (in Table 2 of the inverted fractal spreadsheet file). On the x-axis was the displacement (total distance) of the triangle centre points at each iteration time from t_0 , and on the y-axis, the expansion velocity at each iteration time. A best-fitting linear regression line was calculated, and a Hubble's Law equation (5) was derived

$$v = H_0 d \tag{5}$$

where H_0 is the (present) Hubble constant.

2.3.1 Test Measuring Real Displacement

The propagation of triangles in the (inverted) Koch Snowflake fractal is not linear but in the form of a logarithmic spiral or helical, as shown in Figure 5 (above), and Appendix Figure 17. The method thus far assumes and computes the linear circumference of this spiral rather than the actual displacement (the radius). This method was justified by arguing that the required radius (or displacement) of the logarithmic spiral calculation was too complex to calculate (and beyond the scope of this investigation), and that expansion inferences from the inverted fractal could be made from the linear circumference alone. A spiral model was constructed independently, and radii were measured to assess whether spiral results were consistent with the linear results obtained in the investigation. Measurements were made using geometric software (see Appendix I Figure 17). Displacements and the derived Hubble diagram from this radius model were expected to show significantly lower values than the above (calculated) circumference non-vector method, but share the same (exponential) behaviour. Appendix Figure 1 shows the distance between the centre points, and blue, the displacement. See Appendix Figure 18, and Figure 19, and Table 1 for results.

2.4 Small-Scale Long-Scale Point Distribution Analysis

To address question 4, the number of triangle sizes per total distance increment on the fractal-Hubble diagram was calculated by counting the triangle sizes (in the distance column of Table 2) and dividing this by the total number of distance increments in the sample. See Table 2a of the spreadsheet model. The number of triangles at each increment was calculated by totalling the number of triangles (from Table 4) for each respective iteration-distance. An amended Fractal-Hubble diagram was created combining (recessional) velocity with the number of triangles at every distance. See Table 7 of the spreadsheet model.

3 Results

3.1 Accelerated Area Expansion

The area of the initial triangle of the inverted Koch Snowflake fractal increased exponentially, Figure 6.

The area of the initial triangle bite on the inverted Koch Snowflake fractal increases exponentially with iteration time. cm = centimetres. t = iteration-time.

Figure 6. Initial triangle exponential area expansion.

This expansion, with respect to iteration-time, is written as

$$A = 1e^{2.197t} \quad (6)$$

The area of total area of the fractal (Figure 7 a) and the distance between centre points Figure 7 b) on the fractal increased exponentially.

(a) total area expansion

(b) distance between points. cm = centimetres. t = iteration-time.

Figure 7. Area/distance expansion per iteration time on the Inverted Koch Snowflake fractal.

The expansion of the total area (A^T) is described as

$$A^T = 1.1081e^{2.3032t} \tag{7}$$

The expansion of distance between points (d) is described by the equation

$$d = 0.5549e^{1.2245t} \tag{8}$$

The (recession) velocities for both total area and distance between points—Figure 8 a and b, respectively, increased exponentially per iteration time.

(a) expansion of the total area at each corresponding iteration time (t).

(b) distance between points.

Figure 8. (Expansion) velocity of Area and Points on the Inverted Koch Snowflake Fractal.

Velocity is described by the following equations, respectively

$$v = 1.1908e^{2.2426t} \tag{9}$$

$$v^T = 0.5849e^{1.0986t} \tag{10}$$

where v^T is the (recession) velocity of the total area; and v the (recession) velocity of the distance between points.

The accelerations for both total area and (recession) distance between points—Figure 9 a and b, respectively, increased exponentially per iteration time.

Figure 9. Expansion Acceleration of Area and Distance between Points on the Inverted Koch Snowflake Fractal.

Acceleration is described by the following equations, respectively

$$a^T = 1.1958e^{2.2073t} \tag{11}$$

$$a = 0.5849e^{0.977t} \tag{12}$$

where a^T is the (recession) acceleration of the total area, and a is the (recession) acceleration of the distance between points.

3.2 Inflation Epoch Expansion

From equation (11) it is determined that the development of the fractal takes 72.59 (2s.f.) iteration times to expand from this arbitrarily small area of the Planck area to the arbitrarily large area of 1 cm^{-2} .

$$t = \frac{1}{2.2073} \ln (2.61223 \times 10^{70}) \tag{13}$$

3.3 The Fractal/ Hubble-Lemaitre Diagram

As the distance between centre points increased (with each corresponding iteration-time), the recession velocity of the points also increased—as shown in Figure 10, below.

As the (exponential) distance between triangle geometric centres increases with iteration time, the recession velocity of the points increases. cm = centimetres. t = iteration-time.

Figure 10. The Fractal Hubble-Lemaitre diagram.

The equation describes recession velocity vs. the distance of the fractal

$$v = 0.6667d \tag{14}$$

where the constant factor is measured in units of $cm^{-1}t^{-1} cm^{-1}$.

The spiral radius distance (d), velocity by experiment (see Appendix Figure 18 and Appendix Table 1 for details) produces the Fractal-Hubble equation

$$v = 0.6581d \tag{15}$$

In terms of acceleration vs. distance from the observer, the recession of points accelerated away with increasing distance, as shown in Figure 11 below.

As the distance between the triangle's geometric centres increases with iteration, the recession acceleration of the points increases. cm = centimetres, t = iteration-time.

Figure 11. Recessional Acceleration vs. Distance on the Inverted Koch Snowflake Fractal.

The recession acceleration of points at each iteration time at differing distances on the inverted fractal is described by the equation

$$a = 0.4445d \tag{16}$$

where the constant factor is measured in units of $cm^{-1}t^{-2}$. a = acceleration; d = distance.

The spiral radius displacement (D), acceleration by experiment (see Appendix Figure 19 and Appendix Table 1 for details), was described by the equation

$$a = 0.4295D. \tag{17}$$

Figure 11 shows that the acceleration rate decreases with iteration time, reaching zero at the observer time.

3.4 Distribution of Points and Triangles with Iteration-Time

On the Hubble-fractal diagram (Figure 10), eight of the ten measurement points are located inside the first ($1.20E+4cm^{-1}$) increment distance. The remaining two measurement points are outside this range. Figure 12 shows the quantity of triangles at these 'measurement points' by the distance between the geometric centres (from the observer). The number of triangles decreased exponentially from $7.86E+05$, at the observation point, iteration-distance 0, to a quantity of 1 at a distance of $51800cm^{-1}$ (iteration-10).

As the distance between triangles' geometric centres (exponentially) increases with iteration, and from the observer, the quantity of triangles per iteration decreases exponentially to 1 at iteration-time 0. cm = centimetre.

Figure 12. Count of Triangles at each Distance (Point) from the Observer on the Inverted Koch Snowflake Fractal, first 10 iteration times.

Figure 13 combines the fractal-Hubble diagram (Figure 10) with the quantity of triangles at each distance point (Figure 12) and shows the relationship between the clustering of measurement points close to the (low recessional velocity) origin and the smooth distribution (high recessional velocity) at large distances—towards the origin of the set.

As the distance increases from the observer with respect to iteration time, the recession velocity of the distance between geometric points increases, while the number of triangles at each distance decreases. cm = centimetre.

Figure 13. Fractal-Hubble Centre-Point Distribution Diagram

4 Discussions

The following is a discussion of the empirical experiment conducted on the fractal—from the perspective of an observer within the growing fractal—with respect to cosmology.

4.1 Accelerating Expansion of the Fractal May Explain ‘Dark Energy’ Conjecture

The following refers to question 1 (section 1.2) about the acceleration of the fractal. The acceleration property of the fractal (Figure 9) is consistent with the 1998 astronomical discovery (via observation) of the accelerating, expanding universe and with conjectures surrounding the term ‘dark energy’ and the cosmological constant (λ). It can be inferred (from this inverted fractal model) that the accelerating expansion of the universe concerning distance (Figure 11) is a growth property of fractal geometry, and can be described by the equation

$$a = F_a d \quad (18)$$

where F_a is the fractal (cosmological) recession acceleration constant measured in units of $cm^{-1t-2} cm^{-1}$. The constant F_a in the equation (18) may be interpreted as a fractal, a ‘cosmological constant’—lambda—concerning point acceleration and distance.

The recession acceleration between points with respect to time (equation (12) is described as

$$a = a_0 e^{F\lambda t} \quad (19)$$

where the constant $F\lambda$ may be interpreted as a fractal ‘Cosmological Constant’ Lambda with respect to point acceleration and iteration-time.

With the continual entry of new triangles into the fractal set, the total fractal area of the total universe grows exponentially (Figure 11 above). The function describes this total area expansion with respect to time

$$A^T = A_0 e^{F\lambda t} \quad (20)$$

where $F\lambda$ is a fractal constant with respect to total area expansion and time.

4.2 Fractal Growth Consistent with Inflation Epoch Expansion

The expansion rate of the isolated (unbounded) fractal demonstrates the conjectured early universe “inflation epoch” expansion rate [27]. The opportunity is open to link this expansion with the photon properties of light. Papers on the ‘universe ticking’ of light have conjectured that the ‘ticking’ is at around 10^{-33} per second[28],[29].

If the production of triangle bits by iteration of the fractal is set to correspond to this oscillation frequency or ‘ticking’ of photons, the 72.59 iteration times to expand from the Planck area size to a size of one may be found to be consistent with conjectured inflationary epoch speeds. This is a prediction and an opportunity to develop a better model or to conduct an experiment to test this claim.

4.3 Hubble-Lemaitre Law

The following refers to question 2 (section 1.2) pertaining to (as it was known in its time) Hubble’s Law and the fractal. The shape of the fractal-Hubble curve (Figure 10) has direct significance in Georges Lemaitre’s conjecture surrounding the expanding universe [3] and Edwin Hubble and Humason’s 1929 concurring observations [2]. The fractal model (Figure 10) demonstrates the Hubble-Lemaitre Law, where from any observation point within a fractal, the recession speed of points increases with distance.

The fractal model needs no ‘rising raisin bread’ or ‘rubber sheets’ as used as demonstrations by experts today. When velocity (v) is plotted against the distance of points (D) (Figure 10, and Appendix Figure 18) the inverted fractal demonstrates Hubble’s Law, described by the equation

$$v = F_v D \quad (21)$$

where (F_v) is the slope of the line of best fit, where the fractal (Hubble) recession velocity is constant. The scale invariance of the Fractal-Hubble diagram is consistent with the historical development of the Hubble diagram. From its 1929 original to the improved 1931 version to its most recent form, the diagram’s shape remains constant, as with the fractal model.

4.4 Fractal Explains Small-Scale (and Large-Scale) Galaxy Distribution

The following refers to question 4 (section 1.2) pertaining to the distribution of bit size on the fractal.

Figure 10 (the Hubble-fractal diagram) also shows that the distance between measurement points on the fractal Hubble curve is not linear but increases in an apparently exponential manner. This increase is a consequence of the growth in triangle size. This changing concentration of measured centre points on the diagram is significant in cosmology, as it corresponds to a similar changing distribution of observed galaxies. It pertains directly to the decreasing distribution—the smoothness—of galaxies observed at earlier times. The claimed ‘small-cosmic scale fractality of galaxy distribution’.

If the retrospective observation perspective—from deep within a snowflake fractal—is substituted with an observation from high within a common branching tree (fractal), the clustering of points on the Fractal-Hubble diagram would equally correspond to the clustering of self-similar (sized) branches—in the tree—surrounding the observer. If the observer were to look down, inwards from the outer branches—towards the trunk of the tree — the branch (nodes) quantity would decrease, the volume of the single branches would increase, and the branch ‘clustering’ would smooth out.

In Figure 12 it is shown that the quantity of triangle bits at the origin (iteration 0) on the Fractal-Hubble diagram is 786,432. All of these triangles are of the same size as the observer’s triangle viewing position. This quantity of bits also corresponds to the clustering of the measurement points near the origin of the diagram, and this is due to the location of the observer within the emergent (inverted) fractal and the relative size of these triangle bits near the observer. It is as if the observer is on a branch of a (fractal) tree (see section 4.10) surrounded by branches of similar age and size, and is looking back down to the trunk of the tree, which was the origin of the tree and has now expanded.

Figure 14 shows how the galaxy distribution and demographics from the current DESI map of the universe correspond with a branch distribution on a living fractal, in this case, the common (oak) tree. In (a), the different regions/structures of the universe are highlighted by rings of differing colours, and in (b) and (c), these rings are shown to fit the corresponding parts—from rough to smooth—on the tree fractal, from trunk to twig branches.

(a) The DESI Map of the Universe[23] with observation rings from clustered ‘small scale’ (light blue) to the smooth (large structured LQGs) outer universe (blue and light-yellow rings). (b) Observing from high in the branches of an oak tree (fractal), looking down and back to the trunk with corresponding universe observation rings; (c) observing from the trunk of an oak tree (fractal), looking up and out to the branches.

Figure 14. Non-isotropic and Non-Homogeneous Universe Observations Corresponding with a Living Tree Fractal

The growing tree is a perfect example of a fractal and a real-life metaphor for the inverted fractal model; they share similar properties. Using a tree as an analogy to model the fractal universe does not imply that the universe is exactly a tree structure; it only means that, just as a tree is a fractal structure, the universe, too, appears to be a fractal structure.

4.4.1 LQGs and Large-scale Structure Observations Bough Branches

The 'very large', 'thin' and old large-scale survey structures in the assumed smooth universe concur totally with my model of the fractal. They are the 4 billion light-years in size 'Large Quasar Group'[21] and the 10 billion light-years-sized Hercules—Corona Borealis Great Wall [22]. They represent the large 'bough branches', first out from the CMB 'trunk' of the fractal structure (see section 4.10 and Figure 14c). To support this claim, the LQG structures are very large, and they are also old. They are composed of quasars and are sparsely distributed relative to the small-scale clustered region.

4.5 The Fractal Refutes the—Homogeneous and Isotropic—Cosmological Principle

Cosmological observations are consistent with an in situ fractal perspective. The fractal model (see Figure 14 below) explains why the universe is neither homogenous nor isotropic. The standard model of cosmology's key assumption—the cosmological principle—may be, as it stands today, a mere illusion, a false paradigm.

Before explaining how this fractal model does not conform to the status quo—something that has been continually explained throughout this paper—it should be made clear it is already claimed and granted by cosmologists in their explanations of the cosmological principle that based on modern observations it only holds on large scales—scales larger a redshift z factor of .25 (about 4 billion light-years)—and that on small cosmic scales it does not. The recent discovery of—thinner and older—large quasar groups (LQGs) and the Hercules—Corona Borealis Great Wall (4.4.1) that are beyond this z -factor distance (beyond a z -factor of 4) add strength to the large-scale rebuttal [21],[30]. The following addresses this rebuttal to the cosmological principle.

4.5.1 Homogeneity

From this fractal experiment, distributions are not the same in all directions, but rather the galaxy distribution will diminish with distance and time, as explained in section 4.1. Smoothness will be observed on large—older—scales (towards the trunk), and clustered fractal activity on small—newer—scales (the branches); just as observed looking out from the Earth's position towards the singularity CMB smoothness. Also, as we look back in time, the fractal model concurs with observations and claims made about the evolution of galaxies—evidenced by dark matter halo merger trees structures (section 4.9). This corresponds to the 'old' LQGs discovery also (4.4.1).

4.5.2 Isotropy:

In a fractal, observations will not be the same in all directions; the distribution of observation points within the model will vary substantially across locations. As with a fractal tree (4.10), there is

an obvious trunk to the structure, and there are prominent clusters of branches, which will not be observed isotropically in all directions. The view will be different if viewed from the trunk than if viewed from within the branches. In this fractal model, it remains true that everything is receding away from any observer, but the view will be different—depending on the position of the observer—and thus not necessarily the same in all directions. There is a fractal edge that has grown since the fractal's origin, and this edge appears—by the model—to also be the once 'centre', though this has expanded and is viewed today—in part and consistent with the standard model—as the CMB. All space between this 'edge' and Earth observation is relatively recent, as supported by the evolution of galaxies. See more on the 'centre of the fractal in 4.6.1.

4.6 Beginnings

The following refers to question 3 (section 1.2) and pertains to the origins of the fractal. The expansion of the first single triangle bit in this model demonstrates a 'singularity Big Bang' beginning. Its area starts at an arbitrarily small value and may be set to the Planck area. This simplest of demonstrations is consistent with the observed very cool cosmic microwave background (CMB). It is not an explosion: it is an infinite exponential expansion of the area of the fractal set. This is consistent with descriptions that 'space itself is expanding'. The fractal, in isolation, expands into 'nothing'. The set has a frontier; however, any position beyond this is unattainable. To an observer anywhere in the set, this initial triangle (t_0) will dominate the extreme horizon, but not all observers will see it. If an observer is more than 7 ± 2 iterations distant from (triangle) bit t^0 and observing without any form of technology, to 'zoom' back in iteration-time, the said bit will not be seen: this is the fractal distance. The 7 ± 2 is derived from the classical emergent development of the fractal, as shown in Figure 3, and may be termed the equilibrium iteration count or observable fractal distance.

4.6.1 Centre of the Universe

With respect to the tree fractal analogy (4.10 below), the seedling (beginning) is not in the same place as the branches. The fractal model implies that the beginning occurred at a specific location. This fractal claim is consistent with the standard model's 'the Big Bang is everywhere' claim; however, the space we inhabit on Earth is emergent: it is created and newer, different from the original place from which the fractal began. From this, a discussion over where the universe's centre—its beginning—is may develop.

4.6.2 Emergent History of Matter

A fractal would imply the universe is an emergent structure—the whole is made of many parts—just as a (fractal) tree is made of many branches. This may force us to question the initial conditions of the Big Bang beginning, namely, whether all mass (in the universe) was together in one place and at one time. It could now be argued—from the principles of fractal emergence—that the universe developed/evolved mass from the bottom up with time. It started small, from a seedling and developed structure. However, this does not explain the extreme temperatures claimed.

4.7 The Particle Horizon Problem

Following from 4.2 and 4.7.1, the modelled *retrospective* inverted fractal demonstrates—and is consistent with—space’s ability to expand ‘extremely fast’. If we think about the production of the fractal from the classical fractal perspective

Figure 3 (a) and that this production has a speed, a rate of production that is propagated akin to the propagation of a light photon, then if we compare this speed with the inverted expanding area behind the fractal the complete model makes sense and the claim ‘space expands faster than the speed of light’ as proposed by Albert Einstein in his General Theory of Relativity and as conjectured by inflation theory.

Arbitrary points on the surface of the original—iteration 0—triangle may be assumed to be close enough to assumed to have ‘causal contact’; however, with the exponential expansion of the fractal object, this contact will not remain, and the points will exponentially expand apart at a rate demonstrated from this experiment (4.2). Concerning the speed of light, the fractal has a constant propagation speed (as discussed in 4.7.1 below), this speed can be assumed, in principle, to be able to be surpassed by the (accelerating) area expansion ‘speed’ of the fractal itself. This claim about the fractal expansion rate is also consistent with and addresses issues surrounding the particle horizon problem and the cosmological principle (axiom).

4.7.1 The Fractal and the Speed of Light.

From the ‘classical view’ of the fractal Figure 3A (fully developed in the author’s paper, *The Fractal Corresponds to Light and Quantum Foundation Problems*[1]) from the fractal, there may be a strong insight into the nature and behaviour of light. If this is so, it may help explain why the universe expands and behaves as it does, and also help unify the large-scale universe with its quantum nature.

4.8 Vacuum Catastrophe

Continuing from the above (4.7) the ‘vacuum catastrophe discrepancy’ may also be resolved by understanding the universe as a fractal and that we, the observer, are in one. As described in the introduction, the fractal exhibits a duality of perspectives from an observer: the classical (forward) view and the expanding (behind) view; together, they are different aspects of a single geometry. This investigation focused on the expansion of the fractal and claimed that this expansion is the (dark energy) cosmological constant. The classical aspect—outside this investigation—can be shown to behave as the quantum problem. The classical fractal demonstrates wave-like helical, smaller and smaller (wavelengths), and higher and higher frequencies; while the expansion (behind) is in terms of exponentials. Together, the counterperspectives are divergent and vast, yet they form a single geometry.

From pure application and measurement of the modelled fractal: if a standard fixed area size, for instance, the area of iteration 0 triangle size, is used to calculate the total area of the set, the resulting total area will be very large. However, if the total area of the inverted fractal is divided by the real corresponding area sizes of the expanded triangles (allowing for their expansion at each iteration time), the number will equate to a lower and more realistic number. The total area equals the total

number of triangles propagated in the set. In principle, all triangles are as identical as the iteration 0 standard triangle, and only differ in scale due to the fractal expansion.

4.9 Dark Matter Halo Trees and the Evolution of Stars and Galaxies

Something that is beyond the scope of the investigation—however important enough to mention as the author sees it to be inextricable to the fractal model—is the evolution of galaxy demographics and distribution in the form of Dark Matter halo trees. From a presentation given by Sandra Faber on this subject[31], a fractal interpretation of the universe would give rise to this ‘fractal’ tree structure: from smooth and thin at distant and early distances to rough and clustered at nearby distances.

(a) Diagram showing the age and size structure of the galaxies; that we (Earth) are surrounded by large and old galaxy clusters[31].

(b) The classic Dark Matter Halo tree—evolving from early t₁ (top) to large clusters t₅ (bottom)[31].

Figure 15. Fractal Dark Matter Halo Trees and the Evolution of Atoms, Stars and Galaxies.

The significance of these merger halo structures is that they align with an evolving fractal model of the universe revealed in this study. Halo trees are what one would expect to see if observing within a fractal space.

4.10 Accelerating Growth of Living Fractals—Trees

In support of this observation, a recent publication reported that trees were growing at an accelerating rate [24], [32]. The study measured up to 80 years of tree growth on more than 600,000 trees across six continents and found that the growth of 97 per cent of the trees accelerated with age. This accelerated growth rate with time is a mystery to biologists. The fractal nature of plant growth may explain this phenomenon of accelerated plant growth. Trees and all plants are perfect examples of fractals. A tree’s growth is generally described as being of ‘natural’ fractal geometry. If the productive leafy stem of the emergent tree Figure 16a becomes the focus of the tree’s growth and is held constant in size—just as with the standard triangle size is to the inverted Koch snowflake (Figure

3b)—then the older branches and the load-bearing trunk of the tree will grow exponentially with iteration time—again just as the snowflake did.

Figure 16 a and b show this seedling versus outer branch assumption on a real tree. On the left of Figure 16a, the size of a leaf is of a fully grown/developed tree and in the right of Figure 16 a, shows the leaf size as a seedling. Figure 16b shows the seedling held in a hand alongside the outer leaves and branches leading down to the boughs and the trunk behind.

(a) Showing the one constant on an iterating tree fractal, the leaf size. The left branch is from the outer branches of the fully-grown tree, and the branch on the right is seedling-sized.

(b) The same seedling as in (a—right) is held alongside the outer branch size of a fully developed tree of (a—left). Behind are the trunk, boughs and branches of the same tree. The trunk of the tree, it can be deduced, was once the same size as the seedling in hand.

Figure 16. Fractal Tree Growth from a Constant Leaf Size.

4.11 Raised Questions

4.11.1 Which Fractal Shape?

This investigation does not in any way suggest that the universe has the shape of a tree or a snowflake; fractal expansion could equally have been demonstrated using the Sierpinski triangle. The universe shares a feature special to fractals: fractals come in many forms, and that exact form is beyond the scope of this paper, but it remains a good question.

4.11.2 Addressing Dark Flow, the Great Attractor and Spiralling Universe

At the time of writing, there have been papers published [33]—based on the existence of so-called ‘dark flow’ and the Great Attractor, which appears to be ‘flowing’ in the opposite direction as to ‘dark energy accelerating observations—that challenge the observations pointing to an accelerating universe (and thus the existence of dark energy). The fractal model can address these rebuttals by treating them as part of the fractal system. If an observer is assumed to be within the fractal set (the

universe), then a flow in the opposite direction to the early and older parts of the fractal—as claimed in the paper—is to be expected, even predicted as part of the continued growth of the system.

The fractal model may also indicate helical rotation during growth. This property has recent (2020) support from claims by Kansas State astronomer Lior Shamir[34] that the universe has: ‘..rotated across multiple complex and shifting axes at once...that the spin appeared to change throughout the universe and that...the universe was more consistent and less chaotic in its early days than it is today.’ [35]

4.11.3 Fractals and the Age of the Universe.

The tree (fractal) grows by iteration time, and not solar time. Trees can generally be as old—by counting the tree rings—as several hundreds of years; however, in terms of their fractal iteration age, they may only be some 4 to 7, maybe more, iteration-times old. Could it be that the universe exhibits a similar relationship or paradox between its age and what we observe? Could it be that the age of the universe we observe is not the actual age of it, that it is older?

A fractal universe would suggest the ‘big bang’ evidence, and conjecture is only part of a larger—potentially infinite—‘greater fractal’. Is the CMB a veil concealing the infinite depth behind it? If this is so, what we observe, in terms of galaxies, is all there is; before this is void.

4.11.4 General Relativity and Quantum Gravity

It should be made clear that this fractal model does not yield any new insights regarding gravity. That said, gravity and general relativity may be entirely independent of the universe's observable structure and quantum nature. The inverted fractal model does not affect General Relativity but only its assumptions about the cosmological principle. It is also conceivable that general relativity may need to be adapted to account for the geometry of the fractal. Work has already begun in this area: from noted theorist Laurent Nottale [36],[37] and others [38]. This does not mean (someday) the fractal cannot explain the dark matter, it is; however, beyond the scope of this paper. However, if dark matter is related to galaxies and galaxies to black holes, it may be that black holes are reverse fractals — everything in this model is only in reverse. Dark matter is the reverse of dark energy.

Furthermore, if gravity is assumed not to be a force but rather a consequence of acceleration, the fractal may provide insight into it and dark matter.

4.11.5 Quantum Mechanics (Like) Properties of the Fractal

Viewed from an (arbitrary) fixed position outside the model, the fractal will grow at a decreasing rate to form the classical fractal shape—a snowflake, as shown in Figure 3a. But from the perspective of an observer within the fractal set, as modelled, the same expansion will appear to expand. This assumption of observation from within the set, looking forward from a fixed position, has an uncanny resemblance to properties and problems shared with objects described only by quantum mechanics and the electromagnetic spectrum.

When isolated, the iterating (snowflake) fractal is an infinite number of discrete triangles (bits). The snowflake is a superposition of all triangles, in one place, at one time. The production of new

triangles propagates in the geometry of a spiral: rotating in an arbitrary direction to form—when viewed from a side elevation—a logarithmic sinusoidal wave, comparable to the described electromagnetic spectrum. This spiralling, wave-like propagation is illustrated in Figure 3b and in Appendix Figure 17. Location or position within this infinite set is only known when observed or measured; otherwise, all positions are possible—at the same time. These quantum-like features of the fractal constitute the essential background for this investigation and are discussed in my companion paper, "The Fractal Corresponds to Light and Quantum Foundation Problems" [1]. Together, the dual perspectives will make sense of the universe. This quantum fractal insight, now applied to cosmology, may offer direct insight into the new field of Quantum Cosmology [39].

4.11.6 Inverted Fractal Resemblance to the Atom

Keeping with 4.11.5, mention must be given to the distribution of measurement points made on the Hubble fractal diagram (Figure 10) and how this corresponds with an atomic-like shape where measurement points are concentrated around the origin of the curve, leaving increasing space beyond and out to the edge. This is a scale-free property of the fractal. Significance beyond this observation is outside the scope of this paper.

5 Conclusions

The inverted fractal model is an exquisite and inextricable fit to what is observed and conjectured in the cosmos. This fractal model demonstrates and addresses problems directly associated with the Λ CDM model of cosmology. It is a model of exponential expansion that begins from a single point. From any arbitrary fixed location within a (Koch snowflake) fractal set, the preceding areas of triangle bits expand exponentially at an inextricable hierarchy of sizes. Recession velocity between marked points (on triangles) from 'the observers' perspective also increased exponentially as a function of distance and time. This exponential expansion is a property shared by all irregular/chaotic fractal objects. The fractal model explains the conjectured 'dark energy' accelerated expansion of the universe. The model predicts a cosmological constant and demonstrates a changing acceleration rate ('dark energy') that decreases with time. The fractal offers a geometric mechanism that explains the presence of the CMB and corresponds directly to the conjectured expansion times of the inflationary epoch. There is an opportunity to further test and tie the fractal to the speed and nature of light, and this (inflationary) expansion. The model demonstrated the expansion of space and directly revealed both the Hubble-Lemaitre Law and a diagram. Both observations and the fractal model refute the cosmological principle. The fractal model explains and concurs with the distribution and demographics of galaxies in the observable universe—from the granted 'rough and fractal' on small cosmic scales to the old, large, and thin LQGs structures on large cosmic scales. As a result, the model violates the cosmological principle. We do not observe homogeneity, nor should we expect to in a growing fractal, and the universe is therefore not isotropic.

The fractal model offers a direct geometric solution to the quantum gravity problem, that the quantum and the observed cosmos are different sides of one emergent fractal geometry. Looking 'behind' into the fractal corresponds with cosmological observations; looking 'forward' into the fractal from an in-situ observation point corresponds with 'the quantum'[1]. Together—and with

further exploration—fractal geometry will complete the knowledge gap. The fractal may open the door to a quantum unification and so-called quantum gravity. This simple geometric model does not take away from General Relativity; it complements it. Gravity is independent of the fractal model.

By cosmological observations, the universe is behaving exactly as a growing fractal. Suppose we had no cosmological observations but only the mathematics of fractal geometry to inform predictions about the structure and evolution of our universe; if, based on the ubiquity of fractals in our Earthly reality, we would expect to observe the universe we currently observe. This is not the first time geometry has resolved observational discrepancies or paradoxes; one need only look to how circles, and later ellipses, explained and ended a paradigm. Fractals are the geometry of our time.

Appendix

Displacement is measured between (discrete) triangle centres and used in the calculation of the fractal/Hubble constant. The red line traces the circumference (the distance) of the fractal spiral, and the blue line the displacement of the fractal spiral from an arbitrary centre of observation. cm = centimetres.

Figure 17. Displacement measurements from radii on the iterating Koch Snowflake created with TI-Nspire™ software.

Table 1. Displacement taken from radius measurements and calculations from the iterating Koch Snowflake fractal spiral (Appendix Figure 17).

t	Displacement:	Total Displacement:	Expansion Ratio	Velocity: $cm\ t^{-1}$	Acceleration: $cm\ t^{-2}$	Acceleration Ratio
0			-			
1	1.68	1.68	-	1.68	1.68	
2	4.66	6.34	3.77	4.66	2.98	1.8
3	12.16	18.5	2.92	12.16	7.50	2.5
4	35.4	53.9	2.91	35.40	23.24	3.1

cm = centimetres.t= iteration-time.

From an arbitrary observation point on the inverted (Koch Snowflake) fractal, as the distance between triangle geometric centre points increases, the recession velocity of the points receding away increases. cm = centimetres.t= iteration-time.

Figure 18. The Hubble Fractal Diagram (recessional velocity vs. distance) from radius measurements (Appendix Figure 17).

From a fixed central observation point. Using radius measurements (Appendix Figure 1). As the distance between triangle geometric centres points increases, the recession acceleration of the points receding away increases. cm= centimetres. t = iteration-time.

Figure 19. Recessional acceleration with distance on the inverted Koch Snowflake fractal.

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